

A Flexible Ultrasonic Array System for Inspecting Composite Structures

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ABSTRACT

As the use of composite materials increases, the need for effective and practical nondestructive testing (NDT) techniques for composite structures also increases. A flexible array ultrasonic inspection system represents an innovative approach for detecting defects and damage in composite structures. Advantages of the flexible array include ease of use, rapid automated inspection, vacuum coupling to the surface, and ability to conform to curved surfaces. Since the array elements are at fixed locations, the inspection results can be displayed as easy to interpret C-scan images. The flexible ultrasonic array system has been used to inspect both thin and thick composite structures.

INTRODUCTION

For years, advanced composite materials have been used in weight critical structures, such as aircraft and spacecraft. Composites are widely used in the latest commercial aircraft, such as the A340 and Boeing 777 aircraft, which is explained, in part, by the decreasing material and manufacturing costs [1,2]. The structural characteristics and economic viability of composites have led to greater usage in a wide range of non-aerospace applications, including automobiles, marine structures, and sporting goods. In addition to reduced vehicle weight, which improves fuel economy, composites provide other benefits in automotive applications, including design flexibility, durability, tailorable appearance, and consistent fabricability [3]. Fiberglass reinforced composite materials have been used in marine applications for more than 50 years, due to their high specific strength and stiffness, durability, and resistance to the marine environment. More recently, the Navy is evaluating a variety of applications of composites for surface ships and submarines, including hulls, topside structures, and shipboard machinery [4,5]. Composites are finding increased usage in the infrastructure, as replacements for wooden piers and as reinforcement for concrete highway supports. In the future, concrete structures, including roadways and bridge decks, that have traditionally been reinforced with steel, may be reinforced with composite materials producing lighter, stiffer, stronger, more durable and earthquake resistant structures.

As the use of composites increases, the need for technology to support these structures during manufacturing and service also increases. The aerospace industry has already realized the importance of maintaining composite structures. Charles E. Harris, head of the Mechanics of Materials Branch of the NASA Langley Research Center, recently reported on an assessment of the current practices in supporting composite structures in the commercial air transport fleet [6]. Among the current and future technology needs identified by the study was nondestructive testing (NDT) to assess damage and to qualify repairs. Harris states that "the technology necessary to identify, characterize, and assess damage and the technology to repair a damaged structure are essential partners in aircraft supportability and cost-effective fleet management". As composites

find greater use in a broader range of applications, it is likely that similar technology will be required to support these structures.

NONDESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Ultrasonic inspection is frequently used to detect defects and damage in composite structures. The inspection is typically performed by manually or robotically scanning the surface with a single ultrasonic transducer. A flexible array ultrasonic inspection system represents an innovative approach for ultrasonically inspecting composite structures. Advantages of the flexible array include ease of use, rapid automated inspection, vacuum coupling to the surface, and ability to conform to curved surfaces. Since the array elements are at fixed locations, the inspection results can be displayed as easy to interpret C-scan images.

The flexible array ultrasonic inspection system is a digital system, which facilitates post-processing, storage, and transmittal of inspection data. When indications are found, the images can be transmitted anywhere in the world by modem for evaluation by experts. If a component is scanned with the array immediately after manufacture, the data can be archived and used as a baseline for subsequent field inspections. The system can be used at maintenance facilities and deployed in the field. Arrays can be permanently attached to structures to monitor integrity, to detect damage, and to inspect difficult to access surfaces.

PARIS FLEXIBLE ULTRASONIC ARRAY SYSTEM

The PARIS ultrasonic inspection system consists of a flexible transducer array and the associated display and control electronics. Figure 1 shows a PARIS array with 1024 transducer elements arranged in a 32 by 32 element matrix. The dimensions of the active area of this array are 20- by 20-cm providing a total inspection area of 400 square cm. Inspection time for this array is under one minute.

Figure 1. PARIS Flexible Ultrasonic Array

The geometry and ultrasonic characteristics of the flexible array can be designed and fabricated to meet specific inspection requirements. For example, a long, narrow array can be built to inspect a

bondline or a row of fasteners. The array used to inspect thin composite structures operates at 2.5 MHz, while the array built to inspect thick, highly attenuative composites operates at less than 1 MHz. A flexible array can be built to conform to the complex geometry of a part, such as doubly-curved surfaces. Because the flexible array is vacuum coupled to the surface, couplant may not be necessary for relatively smooth surfaces. In some cases, a light water spray is all that is needed.

The PARIS display and control unit, which is typically built into a portable computer, has a menu-driven operating system. An operator can set the ultrasonic inspection parameters or load predefined inspection parameters from magnetic media. The operator can select the entire array or any subset of the array for scanning, choose from a variety of data display formats, and store data on magnetic media for subsequent recall and display.

PARIS digitizes the complete RF waveform and processes the ultrasonic data in its computer, including 1) time-averaging of the RF waveform to reduce noise, and 2) scanning of the waveform for flaw indications. During scanning, PARIS collects both amplitude and time-of-flight information for each of three gates, which are typically set to monitor front surface, flaw, and back surface echoes. After the transducer array has been scanned, the data can be viewed in a variety of display formats.

Figure 2 shows an inspection of a 737 aircraft using the PARIS system. In the figure, the flexible array is vacuum coupled to the fuselage and the ultrasonic electronics and portable computer are visible in the foreground. This inspection was performed to demonstrate the capabilities of PARIS for inspecting aging aircraft [7].

Figure 2. PARIS Inspection of 737 Aging Aircraft.

INSPECTION OF THIN COMPOSITES

PARIS was originally developed to inspect thin structural composites, specifically the graphite-epoxy components of the Navy's AV-8 aircraft. Figure 3 shows a time-of-flight C-Scan and B-

Scan from an inspection of a composite wing skin on a Navy AV-8B aircraft. In the time-of-flight C-Scan, depth is indicated using the gray scale shown to the right of the image. This scale depicts the depth of an indication by its shade of gray. The darker the shade, the closer the indication is to the front surface. The slight change in shading from top to bottom on the C-Scan indicates a slight change in the thickness of the component across the scan area. A delamination, caused by impact damage, is clearly visible in the center of the C-Scan in Figure 3. The B-scan displays a cross-section through the part at the location indicated by the cursor in the C-scan.

Figure 3. PARIS Inspection of AV-8B Wing Skin Impact Damage

A PARIS system was recently developed to inspect composite structures on commercial aircraft in a maintenance facility. The specification for this system included a requirement to inspect each ply in a 30-ply laminate. A flexible array specifically designed for this application successfully met this resolution requirement.

INSPECTION OF THICK COMPOSITES

The goal of current research for the Army Tank Automotive Command (TACOM) is to adapt the flexible ultrasonic array technology to inspect thick composites, such as the multi-layer composite structure currently being evaluated for the Army's Composite Armored Vehicle Technology Demonstrator (CAV) [8]. Capabilities are needed to inspect multi-layer structures for manufacturing defects in the factory and for service damage in the field. The technical approach for this specific adaptation is to increase ultrasonic penetration by 1) fabricating an array that operates at a lower frequency and at a higher voltage than is typically used for thin composites; and 2) employing a synthetic pulse technique. The synthetic pulse technique alters the transmitted ultrasonic spectrum, which optimizes the pulse shape in the returned signals and improves resolution.

A prototype flexible array was fabricated to inspect thick composite armor material. For glass fiberglass composite material, ultrasonic attenuation increases rapidly as the frequency is increased beyond about 700 KHz. Accordingly, a key design goal for the transducer array was an operating frequency range from 400 KHz to 900 KHz. The measured frequency response for the prototype array is approximately 350 KHz to 900 KHz, which meets the design specification at both the lower and upper frequency limits. The frequency response is very flat over the bandwidth of interest resulting in good performance for synthetic pulse applications.

The prototype array and synthetic pulse technique were used to inspect fiberglass panels ranging from 1.27 to 2.54 cm thick and containing urethane inserts at different depths, as shown in Figure 4. For the 2.54 cm panel, the reconstructed waveform (Figure 5) shows both the front and rear surface reflection. Figure 6 shows the waveform from a 1.27 cm diameter insert located 1.27 cm deep in the 2.54 cm thick panel. These figures illustrate the capacity of the prototype array to detect

defects in the thick composite armor material. Future work involves incorporating these same capabilities into a full-size array and PARIS ultrasonic inspection system to be delivered to TACOM.

Figure 4. Thick S-2 Glass Panel with Urethane Inserts

Frequency Sweep		Equivalent Time Scan	
Start (MHz)	0.400	Total Scan (usec)	200.000
End (MHz)	1.200	Sample Interval (usec)	0.098
Step Size (MHz)	0.005		
Max Freq (MHz)	5.120		

Figure 5. Waveform from 2.54 cm Thick Fiberglass Panel

Frequency Sweep		Equivalent Time Scan	
Start (MHz)	0.400	Total Scan (usec)	200.000
End (MHz)	1.200	Sample Interval (usec)	0.098
Step Size (MHz)	0.005		
Max Freq (MHz)	5.120		

Figure 6. Waveform from 2.54 cm Thick Fiberglass Panel:
1.27 cm Diameter Insert 1.27 cm Deep

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IMPACT BEHAVIOUR
